

D3.2 Stakeholders Mapping and Scouting

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Work Package	WP3
Delivery Date (DoA)	31st July 2023
Actual Delivery Date	18th July 2023

Document Revision History			
Date	Version	Author/Contributor/Reviewer	Summary of Main Changes
31 st May 2023	0.1	Martin VLACHYNSKY, Robert MISKUF	Table of contents and first version
30 th s June	0.2	Letizia PIRAS	Revision of the first version
5 th July	0.3	Robert MISKUF	Formatting and typos
10 th July	0.4	Anna Torz	Formatting
13 th July	0.5	Letizia Piras	Formatting
14 th July	1.0	Robert MISKUF	Final version

Dissemination Level and Nature of the Deliverable		
PU	Public	x
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
Nature	R = Report, E = Ethics or, O = Other	R

BUILD Consortium			
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2	CIVITTA EESTI AS	CE	EE
3	CITY OF TURKU	Turku	FI
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BUILD

Building Capacities in Innovation Procurement for Cities

Grant Agreement: 101070745

Funding Scheme: HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions (CSA)

Theme: HORIZON-EIE-2021-CONNECT-01-02

Start Date of Project: 01 October 2022

Duration: 24 months

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
BUILD	Building Capacities in Innovation Procurement for Cities
GDPR	Grant Data Protection Regulation
GPP	Green Public Procurement
NUTS	Classification of territorial units for statistics
PCP	Pre Commercial Procurement
PP	Public Procurement
PPI	Public Procurement of Innovation
SPP	Sustainable Public Procurement
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

The aim of Task 3.2 is to provide an overview of the actors to be mobilised and engaged in BUILD activities to facilitate connections and networks between buyers and suppliers. This goal will be met by identifying the relevant stakeholders and employing clustering techniques. This task will enable the targeted involvement in the BUILD activities and prepare the support activities within Work Package 3 (WP3) and pilot Public Procurement of Innovation (PPI) initiatives within Work Package 4 (WP4). Moreover, an objective of this task is to identify and mobilize additional actors who possess the potential to facilitate and provide expert guidance in the context of the Innovation Procurement process. These connections will support the establishment of new partnerships and consortia among suppliers to increase the knowledge exchange and joint participation to PPIs. This activity will be supported by other related projects and initiatives performed in the context of the informal Innovation Procurement Task Force.

The leadership for this task is taken by PEDAL, supported by contribution partners, namely CE, Turku, and Tartu City.

2 BUILD Stakeholder mapping & scouting methodology

2.1 Categories and criteria assessment

The Methodology used for stakeholder mapping and scouting includes the following steps:

i. Assessing the stakeholders categories

The stakeholders were categorised in the following four groups, taking into consideration their role within the arena of procurement of innovate:

1. Public and private buyers, procurers, named “Innovation demand”: this category refers to entities or individuals, both from the public and private sectors, who have a need or demand for innovative products, services or solutions. They are the potential customers or clients that seek out innovative solutions to address specific challenges or meet certain requirements.

2. SMEs, start-ups, spin-offs, universities, incubators, and technology centres, named “Innovation Supply”: they are the key players in the innovation ecosystem who contribute to the development and supply of innovative products, services, or solutions. They are often involved in research, development, and commercialisation of new technologies or ideas.

3. Other relevant actors: Intermediaries, Lobbies, Associations, Advisors, Policy Makers, named “Multipliers”. This category encompasses various stakeholders who play a significant role in facilitating and supporting innovation activities. They could be interested in both innovation supply and demand stakeholders.

4. Projects related to Innovation Procurement, named “Projects”: this category refers to specific initiatives or endeavours focused on innovation procurement. Projects in this can include activities such as developing procurement strategies, conducting market research, defining requirements, managing procurement processes, and evaluating the impact of innovation procurement initiatives.

ii. Identification of clustering criteria

For all stakeholder types it was required to collect the Organisation name, website, geographical information (town, country), protected data (e-mail, telephone, name). Personal data includes data with contacts that gave consent or are publicly shared, in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). In order to provide a full analysis of the potential level of engagement of a selected stakeholder, information regarding the collaboration history and potential interest and motivation regarding BUILD tasks were used.

A specific set of criteria was designed for each category.

1. Innovation Demand

Criteria	Options	Definition
Innovation Demand	Individual Public Buyer	
	Central Purchasing body	
	Regional Purchasing body	
	Private Purchasing body(not direct target)	
	Other	
Level of activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • City level • Regional • Transregional • National • EU • International • N/A 	
NUTS 2021 classification:	NUTS 1	Major socio-economic regions
	NUTS 2	Basic regions for the application of regional policies

	NUTS 3	Small region for specific diagnoses
Estimated yearly budget for procurement of innovation	Small	Up to 10% of the annual budget
	Medium	Up to 25% of the annual budget
	Large	More than 25% of the annual budget

Table 1. Clustering criteria for Innovation Demand

2. Innovation Supply

Application field of their innovation relevant for BUILD:

- Green mobility
- Bioeconomy
- Circular economy
- Education
- Company training

3. Multipliers

Multiplier stakeholder type:

Criteria	Option
Activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intermediary • National centre for public administration training • Industrial cluster • Investor/alternative financing • Associations/lobby • Advisors/consultancy/legal • Policy maker • Trade union/civil society • European institution • Media • Other
Level of activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • City level • Regional • Transregional • National • International • EU • N/A

Table 2. Clustering criteria for Multipliers

4. Projects

Criteria	Options
State	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ongoing • Concluded
Area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovation Procurement • Health • Climate change • Circular economy
Domain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public Procurement of Innovation (PPI) • Pre Commercial Procurement (PCP) • Public Procurement (PP) • Green Public Procurement (GPP) • Sustainable Public Procurement (SPP)
Programme	
Start and end date	
Coordinator	
Coordinator country	
Projects assets and links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reports • Tools • Events to be exploited

Table 3. Clustering criteria for Projects

2.2. Creation of the database

Once the criteria were identified, a shared spreadsheet was created, containing all the information provided in points (i) and (ii). The motivation behind using this tool is linked to the need to have an online shared document where all BUILD project partners could fill in the information and participate in the mapping & scouting activity. Any BUILD project partner filling the spreadsheet with a stakeholder contact was asked to sign as a “Responsible partner” in the designated box, serving as a main contact reference. To easily and promptly assess the stakeholder activities, a short description of them was described in the specific box.

The detailed structure of the database is available in detail in section 3.

2.3 Analysis and collection of stakeholders details through an online research

The research was performed using, among others, the following sources:

1. Innovation Procurement Platform¹:

¹ https://innovation-procurement.org/resources/?c=search&category=project_initiative

It is a platform developed under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 780192. The content present in this website is responsibility of the Procure2Innovate project (BUILD is in regular contact with the Procure2Innovate coordinator). It provides a database of resources, case studies, guidance and projects related to innovation procurement.

2. The European Innovation Council and Small and Medium-sized Enterprises Executive Agency (EISMEA)²:

It has developed this interactive tool that generates information on EU funding programmes. The application is available for the following programmes managed by the Agency: European Innovation Council, COSME, Innosup, European Innovation Ecosystem. The filters enable a quick and precise research.

3. The European Assistance For Innovation Procurement (EAFIP)³:

It is an initiative financed by the European Commission (DG CONNECT) for providing local assistance to public procurers for starting new innovation procurement and for promoting good practices and reinforcing the evidence base on completed innovation procurements. It is coordinated and led by Corvers Procurement Services. The website provides a collection of webinars and events through which it was possible to trace the stakeholders involved.

4. Procure2Innovate Project:

The project aims to improve institutional support for public procurers of information and communication technologies (ICT) and other sectors that implement innovation procurement. The project will establish or expand competence centres of innovation procurement in 10 European Union countries: Austria, Germany, Netherlands, Spain, Sweden, Estonia, Greece, Ireland, Italy and Portugal.⁴

5. PROTECT project:

The project supports urgent action for climate adaptation, mitigation and resilience. It enables public authorities to use state-of-the-art public procurement approaches to identify solutions. At the policy level, it aims to provide decision makers for procurement, climate and policy at the EU, national, regional and local levels, with practical recommendations and guidelines to boost the use of innovation procurement for climate action.⁵

6. The Urban Agenda for the EU:

The Urban Agenda for the EU represents a new multi-level working method, for urban policy and practice, promoting cooperation between Member States, cities, the European Commission, and other stakeholders.⁶

7. CircularPSP project:

² <https://sme.easme-web.eu/#>

³ <https://eafip.eu/about/>

⁴ P2I | European network of competence centres for innovation procurement (procure2innovate.eu)

⁵ PROTECT (protect-pcp.eu)

⁶ Urban Agenda for the EU | EUI (urban-initiative.eu)

CircularPSP brings together 7 procurers from 7 countries, representing 45 million citizens, to invest €5.64 million in R&D to tackle the common challenge of accelerating the digital transition towards a Circular Economy (CE). The Buyers Group represents highly attractive national markets (Germany, Finland, Turkey, Sweden, Ireland, Portugal, Slovenia) supported by a Preferred Partner in UK, including capitals with global influence (Berlin, Helsinki, London, Istanbul). The consortium represents European CE- transition and PCP leaders in science and practice.⁷

8.The European Institute for Innovation and Technology (EIT):

The EIT's mission is to create jobs and deliver sustainable and smart growth. It is an integral part of Horizon Europe. Its method consists in bringing together organisations across business, education, and research. The goal is to find and commercialise solutions to pressing global challenges.⁸

9. InnoFacilitator project:

The project will demonstrate the relevance and effectiveness of cooperation between various stakeholders, supporting innovation actors (start-ups and SMEs) in healthcare to access public procurement, and supporting the public and private buyers (hospitals, regional and local authorities, public and private purchasing centres) to launch Public Procurement of Innovation (PPI).⁹

10. The Community research and development Information Service (CORDIS):

The Community Research and Development Information Service (CORDIS) is the European Commission's primary source of results from the projects funded by the EU's framework programmes for research and innovation, from FP1 to Horizon Europe.¹⁰

11. CimArk Innovation Community:

It is an innovation consultancy focused on providing innovation support for SMEs, coaching activities and support to funding research. It has a broad partnership working in different fields of innovation.¹¹

12. ProCirc project:

The project aims to advance circular procurement through key scaling strategies. It fosters Transnational and Cross-Industry Communities of Practice to facilitate knowledge exchange and sustainable partnerships.¹²

Stakeholders from any categories were analysed with the main purpose to find companies or entities that focus on public procurement of innovation and that are still existing and working. Regarding this detail, it is to be noted that concluded projects were mapped as well since their coordinator or partner entities can represent potential contacts to be engaged in the BUILD projects future activities of WP4.

⁷ Circular-PSP - Home (circularpsp.eu)

⁸ European Institute of Innovation & Technology (EIT) | EIT (europa.eu)

⁹ InnoFacilitator

¹⁰ .CORDIS | European Commission (europa.eu)

¹¹ CimArk – EBN | EU| BIC Innovation Community

¹² ProCirc, Interreg VB North Sea Region Programme

i. Analysis of stakeholders' activities and partners, mapping of their networks and relevant entities, data collection

Each research result was analysed to collect the information mentioned in (ii) as well as assessing other initiatives or partners that were not mapped in the websites mentioned in (iv). This activity was useful to enrich the database with existing networks in public procurement of innovation as well as identifying partners with the same level of engagement.

ii. Stakeholders data collection through the existing networks of the BUILD project's partners

All BUILD project partners were asked to contribute to the Mapping & Scouting activity by providing their existing contacts and details of any stakeholder category. The type of relation between the two parties could include both previously existing collaborations or acquaintances due to professional activities or geographical proximity.

3. Database

The database was made using a shared spreadsheet document. Each category's information was collected in its respective sheet. The spreadsheet contains also the instructions to fill in the relevant information in order to ensure all BUILD project partners a good understanding of the procedure and to have a successful coordinated action.

The database descriptions followed the instructions from points (i) and (ii)

As an internal working document, it was saved under the shared repository BUILD project folder, to ensure accessibility to all project partners.

A	B
BUILD Stakeholders mapping template: Instructions	
Step1 (Drop down menus with groups identification)	
	<i>Please read all the categories and subcategories in drop down menus. You are most welcome to identify a new stakeholder group and / or subgroup. In this case, please include your addition(s) in the respective fields.</i>
Step2 (Main Template)	<i>Please provide information for all the stakeholders. Stakeholders could be organisations, communities, individuals or related project. Please fill in all required fields according to the guidelines provided below:</i>
4 sheets	There are four main categories of stakeholders - 1.sheet - Innovation Demand, 2.sheet - Innovation Supply, 3.sheet - Multipliers + Other, 4.sheet Projects/Initiatives. As a first step, please choose under which one your information will go.
Stakeholder type	Choose the type form the drop down menu
Level of activity	Choose if they are active on national/international/EU, etc level based on the drop down menu
NUTS 2021 clasification	NUTS 2021 is the Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics - hierarchical system for dividing up the economic territory of the EU and the UK for the purpose of the collection, development and harmonisation of European regional statistics and socio-economic analyses of the regions.
BUILD Partner name	The name of your organisation (drop down menu)
Stakeholder/Organisation name	The stakeholder's organisation name
Organisation details	Fill in all the details that you can - website, town, country, info on collaboartion history, if any
Contact details	Please keep in mind GDPR and include information only from people that we received consent to be contacted/included, etc for some activities (such as form surveys) and contact that are publically available.
Potential interest and motivation	Include information for which Tasks/activities the stakeholder/organisation could be interested. What the stakeholder could most likely contribute to? What does PROCEDIN need from this stakeholder?
Projects	Include as much information as you can, including the general information if the project is ongoing (O) or concluded (C), project's website, cordis'website, acronym and full project name, its area and any specific information to determine possible synergies and/or use of resources
Projects - Relevant for collaboration	Please rate yes, no, maybe

Figure 1. Instructions

Type					Responsible partner		Shared Contact Data			
Innovation Demand stakeholder type*	Level of activity*	NUTS 2021 classification	Estimated yearly budget for procurement of innovation (if available)	Short description* (to help better define the collaboration strategy in BUILD)	BUILD partner* (main contact)	Organisation name*	Website*	Town*	Country*	Collaboration history (please use this cell to keep track of contacts/interest)
Individual Public buyer	City level	NUTS 3: small regions for specific diagnoses	Small (up to 10% of the annual budget)	The University of Tartu is biggest organisation in Tartu City and one of the biggest procurer	City of Tartu	Tartu University	https://ut.ee/en	Tartu	Estonia	
Other	National	NUTS 1: major socio-economic regions	No budget allocated	Supporting companies	City of Tartu	Estonian Business and Innovation Agency	https://eas.ee/en/	Tallinn	Estonia	
Other	National	NUTS 1: major socio-economic regions	No budget allocated	The Estonian Chamber of Commerce and Industry (ECCI) is the oldest and largest Estonian representative organization of entrepreneurs	City of Tartu	Estonian Chamber of Commerce and Industry	https://www.koda.ee/en	Tallinn	Estonia	
Central Purchasing body	National	NUTS 1: major socio-economic regions	No budget allocated	A non-profit limited company, and act as a central purchasing body for central and local governments in Finland.	Valonia	Hansel	https://www.hansel.fi/en/	Helsinki	Finland	
Regional Purchasing body	Regional	NUTS 1: major socio-economic regions	No budget allocated	A municipality in Southwest Finland region. Turku is doing procurement co-operation with regional municipalities.	City of Turku	Aura	https://aura.fi/	Aura	Finland	
Regional Purchasing body	Regional	NUTS 1: major socio-economic regions	No budget allocated	A municipality in Southwest Finland region. Turku is doing procurement co-operation with regional municipalities.	City of Turku	Kaarina	https://kaarina.fi/	Kaarina	Finland	
Regional Purchasing body	Regional	NUTS 1: major socio-economic regions	No budget allocated	A municipality in Southwest Finland region. Turku is doing procurement co-operation with regional municipalities.	City of Turku	Kemiönsaari	https://www.kemionsaari.fi/	Kemiönsaari	Finland	
Regional Purchasing body	Regional	NUTS 1: major socio-economic regions	No budget allocated	A municipality in Southwest Finland region. Turku is doing procurement co-operation with regional municipalities.	City of Turku	Koski TL	https://koski.fi/	Koski TL	Finland	
Regional Purchasing body	Regional	NUTS 1: major socio-economic regions	No budget allocated	A municipality in Southwest Finland region. Turku is doing procurement co-operation with regional municipalities.	City of Turku	Kustavi	https://kustavi.fi/	Kustavi	Finland	
Regional Purchasing body	Regional	NUTS 1: major socio-economic regions	No budget allocated	A municipality in Southwest Finland region. Turku is doing procurement co-operation with regional municipalities.	City of Turku	Laitila	https://www.laitila.fi/	Laitila	Finland	
Regional Purchasing body	Regional	NUTS 1: major socio-economic regions	No budget allocated	A municipality in Southwest Finland region. Turku is doing procurement co-operation with regional municipalities.	City of Turku	Lieto	https://lieto.fi/	Lieto	Finland	
Regional Purchasing body	Regional	NUTS 1: major socio-economic regions	No budget allocated	A municipality in Southwest Finland region. Turku is doing procurement co-operation with regional municipalities.	City of Turku	Loimaa	https://www.loimaa.fi/	Loimaa	Finland	
Regional Purchasing body	Regional	NUTS 1: major socio-economic regions	No budget allocated	A municipality in Southwest Finland region. Turku is doing procurement co-operation with regional municipalities.	City of Turku	Marttila	https://marttila.fi/	Marttila	Finland	

Protected Data (for GDPR, include data with contacts that gave consent or are publically shared)				Potential interest and motivation (Related to BUILD Tasks). This will help us to map the stakeholders to be involved in the different BUILD activities (add X, when applicable)							
e-mail	other contacts (tel)	First name	Last Name	T3.3 Engagement & Onboarding (M10-M14)	T4.1 Training of Public Procurers (M14-M18)	T4.2 Staff Exchanges to Stimulate Mutual Learning (M18-M21)	T4.3 PPI Simulations & consolidated training approach and updated training material for procurers (M21-M24)	T5.2 Communication and dissemination tools & activities (M1-M24)	T5.3 Development of Communication Materials (M1-M24)	T5.4 Exploitation and Sustainability (M3-M24)	Other (specify)

Figure 2. Innovation Demand sheet, all data categories

Application field of their innovation relevant for BUILD*	Short description of the innovation proposed* (to help better define the collaboration strategy in BUILD)	Responsible partner		Shared Contact Data				
		BUILD partner*	Organisation name*	Website*	Town*	Country*	Registered in Tenderio (Y/N)	Collaboration history (please use this cell to keep track of contacts/interest)
Green mobility	develops, manufactures and sells heating systems for vehicles and other applications. The increasing pressure for more efficient and greener heating systems encouraged Kabola to develop Kabola Blue Ecoline (KB Eco) series.	PEDAL	KABOLA HEATING SYSTEMS BV	https://kabilaheaters.nl/en/home-english/	Vianen	Netherlands		
Bioeconomy	FINISHING LEATHER WITH BIOPOLYMERS ADDED WITH NANOCOMPONENTS	PEDAL	A.L.P.A. - AZIENDA LAVORAZIONE PRODOTTI AUSILIARI S.P.A.	http://www.alpachem.com/		Italy		
Circular economy	Recycling shredded used tyres and rubber waste into personalized recovered Carbon Black to limit use of fossil fuels and carbon dioxide emission	PEDAL	SYNTOIL SPOLKA AKCYJNA	https://www.syntoil.pl/	Wroclaw	PL		
Circular economy	FINISHING LEATHER WITH BIOPOLYMERS ADDED WITH NANOCOMPONENTS	PEDAL	A.L.P.A. - AZIENDA LAVORAZIONE PRODOTTI AUSILIARI S.P.A.	ALPA – Lavorazioni prodotti ausiliari (alpachem.com)	MILANO	IT		
Company training	Innovative model of a simultaneous translation service	PEDAL	ABLIO S.R.L.	Ablio :: Communication Without Barriers	ROMA	IT		
Circular economy	Whey2Value: Valorising waste whey into high-value products	PEDAL	ACIES BIO BIOTEHNOLOSKE RAZISKAVE IN RAZVOJ DOO	AciesBio - Contact	LIUBLJANA	SI		
Bioeconomy	Innovative Biodegradable PLA Plastic for an Increased Range of Packaging Applications	PEDAL	ADVANCED & FUNCTIONAL TECHNOLOGIES FOR BIOCOMPOSITES SL	Bioplásticos y aditivos - 100% COMPOSTABLES - ADBioplastics	PATERNA	ES		
Bioeconomy	Commercialisation of expanded bed biofilm reactor technology for the treatment of waste-	PEDAL	ADVANCED BIOPROCESS DEVELOPMENT LIMITED	Advanced Bioprocess Development (bioprocesses.co.uk)	MANCHESTER	UK		
Bioeconomy	INNOVATIVE FUNCTIONAL PAINT FOR AIR PURIFICATION	PEDAL	ADVANCED MATERIALS SRL	APM Home Page (apmlab.com)	LAIVES	IT		
Circular economy	Arena-Master Mobile Solution for Complete Synthetic Turf Recycling On-site	PEDAL	ADVANCED SPORTS INSTALLATIONS EUROPE AS	(20) Advanced Sports Installations Europe AS. informazioni LinkedIn	TALLINNA	EE		
Circular economy	Mushroom and biogas production in a circular economy	PEDAL	ADVANCED SUBSTRATE TECHNOLOGIES AS	Advanced Substrate Technologies - Recycle Waste - Reuse Bio Substrate - Green Solutions (astech.dk)	TIELE	DK		
Circular economy	Application of Microbial Fuel Cells for waste water treatment	PEDAL	AENEAM ADVANCED MEMBRANE TECHNOLOGIES SOCIEDAD DE RESPONSABILIDAD	AENEAM Advanced Membrane Technologies Sl	ZARAGOZA	ES		
Circular economy	Green Desalination: A closed-loop technology for full recovery of water and raw materials from the wastewater effluent	PEDAL	AEPHORIA NETWORK PC		ATHENS	EL		
Bioeconomy	Innovative biopesticides production: valorisation of endemic plants and green industrial residues	PEDAL	AGROINDUSTRIAL KIMITEC SL	Página de Inicio Kimitec.com	ROQUETAS DE MAR	ES		
Bioeconomy	Development of eco-friendly architectural coil coatings for clean buildings and pollution-free air	PEDAL	ALCEA-AZIENDA LOMBARDA COLORI E AFFINI SPA	Contatti - Alcea - English	SENAGO MI	IT		
Circular economy	INTERnational COMmercialization of innovative products based on Microalgae	PEDAL	ALGAENERGY SA	World leader in microalgae biotechnology (algaenergy.com)	ALCOBENDAS MADRID	ES		
Circular economy	Farming high value algae with industrial gas emissions	PEDAL	ALGING AMBIENTACIONES SL		BARRIKA	ES		

e-mail	other contacts (tel)	First name	Last Name	T3.3 Engagement & Onboarding (M10-M14)	T4.1 Training of Public Procurers (M14-M18)	T4.2 Staff Exchanges to Stimulate Mutual Learning (M18-M21)	T4.3 PPI Simulations & consolidated training approach and updated training material for procurers (M21-M24)	T5.2 Communication and dissemination tools & activities (M1-M24)	T5.3 Development of Communication Materials (M1-M24)	T5.4 Exploitation and Sustainability (M3-M24)	Other (specify)

Figure 3. Innovation Supply sheet, all data categories

Type				Responsible partner		
Multiplier stakeholder type*	Level of activity*	Short description of their activity*	Why relevant for BUILD* (to help better define the collaboration strategy in BUILD)	BUILD partner*	Organisation name*	Website*
Advisors/consultancy/legal	National	Procurio provides public procurement services for both the public and private sectors. It specializes in electronic public procurement, the electronicization of public procurement processes as well as the optimization of public procurement management in the organization.		Valonia	Procurio	https://procurio.sk/
Intermediary (e.g. chambers of commerce, development agencies)	International	VTT is one of Europe's leading research institutions. We are owned by the Finnish state. We advance the utilisation and commercialisation of research and technology in commerce and society. Through scientific and technological means, we turn large global challenges into sustainable growth for businesses and society.	Research and expertise on innovation procurement. Wide network.	Valonia	VTT	www.vttresearch.com/en
National center for Public Administration training	National	Motiva provides the public sector, businesses, municipalities and consumers with information, solutions and services that allow them to make resource-efficient, effective and sustainable choices	National networks, training and tools related to sustainable procurement.	Valonia	Motiva	https://www.motiva.fi/en/motiva
Other	National	Government organisation for innovation funding and trade, travel and investment promotion.	Funding for innovation procurement, related clusters and networks.	Valonia	Business Finland	https://www.businessfinland.fi/en/for-fin-nish-customers/home
National center for Public Administration training	National	KEINO is a network-based Competence center for Sustainable and Innovative public procurement in Finland	Excellence network, events and tools for public procurers	Valonia	Keino	https://www.hankintakeino.fi/en
Policy Maker	National	An advocate for all Finnish municipalities, promotes local self-government and the modernisation of municipal services.	Network and excellence (procurement, legal) related to municipalities	Valonia	Kuntaliitto (ALFRA)	https://www.localfinland.fi/
Other	National	The Finnish Environment institute (Syke) offers expertise and independent information on global phenomena such as climate change, biodiversity loss, overconsumption, pollution and eutrophication.	Research on sustainable procurement	Valonia	SYKE	https://www.syke.fi/en-US
Other	EU	A higher education institution of 12,000 experts, researchers, students, faculty members and teaching professionals. Creates solutions locally and globally. As a significant regional actor, we harbour close ties to businesses and municipalities in Southwest Finland. Turku UAS is the fourth largest technical university in Finland.	Research on procurement. Local networks and case studies. Business and innovation development.	Valonia	Turku University on Applied Sciences TUAS	https://www.tuas.fi/en/
Intermediary (e.g. chambers of commerce, development agencies)	Regional	Turku Science Park Ltd. is a non-profit development company for the entire Turku subregion that works in close cooperation with local, national and international actors in the fields of business and economic development.	Local business networks and innovation development excellence.	Valonia	Turku Business Region	https://turkubusinessregion.com/en/
National center for Public Administration training	National	The main objective of the Enterprise Estonia is to support entrepreneurship and the improvement of living conditions in Estonia, increase our international competitiveness, visibility and attractiveness as a place for business, living and studies.	Excellence center for Estonia	CIVITTA	Trade and Innovation Centre, Enterprise Estonia	https://eas.ee/en/

Shared Contact Data				Protected Data (for GDPR, include data with contacts that gave consent or are publically shared)			
Town*	Country*	Registration in Tenderio (Y/N)	Collaboration history (please use this cell to keep track of contacts/interest)	e-mail	other contacts (tel)	First name	Last Name

Potential interest and motivation (Related to BUILD Tasks)								
T3.3 Engagement & Onboarding (M10-M14)	T4.1 Training of Public Procurers (M14-M18)	T4.2 Staff Exchanges to Stimulate Mutual Learning (M18-M21)	T4.3 PPI Simulations & consolidated training approach and updated training material for procurers (M21-M24)	T5.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan(M1-M3)	T5.2 Communication and dissemination tools & activities (M1-M24)	T5.3 Development of Communication Materials (M1-M24)	T5.4 Exploitation and Sustainability (M3-M24)	Other (specify)

Figure 4. Multipliers sheet, all data categories

Ongoing/ Conclude d O/C	Relevant for collaboration Y/N/M (Maybe)	Project Title		Area	Domain	website	Website (cordis)	Programme	Start date	End date	Coordinator	Country	project focus
		Project Acronym	Full name										
O	Y	BUILD	Building Capacities in Innovation Procurement for Cities	innovation procurement	PPI	https://www.build-procurement.eu/	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101070745	HORIZON.3.2 - European innovation ecosystems	01/10/2022	30/09/2022	PEDAL Consulting	Slovakia	Increase capacities of cities in innovation procurement - providing advisory services to innovation procurement specialists (trainings, staff exchanges, PPI simulations) to encourage cooperation and knowledge sharing between public buyers; help to discover the innovative technological solutions and assist in their development and acquisition by enhancement of innovation knowledge and skills within buyers.
O	Y	InnoFacilitator	Health InnoFacilitator the European Facilitator Community Promoting Public Procurement of Innovation in Healthcare	Health	IP	http://www.innofacilitator.eu/	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101070831	HORIZON.3.2 - European innovation ecosystems	01/10/2022	30/09/2022	MEDICEN	France	
O	Y	PROTECT	Preparing a Pre-Commercial Procurement for end-user services based on environmental observation in the area of climate change adaptation and mitigation	climate change, earth observation	IP	https://www.protect-pcp.eu/	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060592	HORIZON.2.6 - Food, Bioeconomy Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment	01/06/2022	31/05/2024	G.A.C. Group	Europe/ EU	
O	M	CircularPSP	Public Service Platforms for Circular, Innovative and Resilient Municipalities through PCP	circular economy	PCP							Europe/ EU	
O	Y	InnoBuyer	Fast track to innovation procurement		PPI	https://innobuyer.eu/	https://innobuyer.eu/		01/09/2022	31/08/2025	F&S	Europe/ EU	InnoBuyer brings together big organizations (Challengers) and innovative SMEs (Solvers) to jointly co-create innovative solutions, through a lean new model of innovation procurement.
O	Y	CITIES 4.0	Climate Innovation Through Interactive Ecosystem Summits		PPI		https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101070827	HORIZON.3.2 - European innovation ecosystems	01/09/2022	30/04/2024	BRAINPORT DEVELOPMENT NV	Europe/ EU	
C	Y	Procure2Innovate	European network of competence centres for innovation procurement	competence centers		https://procure2innovate.eu/home/	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/780192/it	H2020-EU.2.1.1. - INDUSTRIAL LEADERSHIP	01/01/2018	30/06/2022	BUNDESVERBAND MATERIALWIRTSCHAFT, EINKAUF UND LOGISTIK EV	Germany	Network that was creating an EU wide network of national competence centres on innovation procurement. The network was spearheaded by five countries that are reinforcing existing national competence centers (Germany, Austria, Netherlands, Spain, Sweden) and five countries that were setting up new competence centers (Portugal, Greece, Ireland, Estonia, Italy).
C	M	AI4Cities	AI accelerating Cities transition to carbon neutrality	artificial intelligence, carbon neutrality of cities	PCP	https://ai4cities.eu/	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/871814	H2020-EU.2.1.1. - INDUSTRIAL LEADERSHIP	01/01/2020	31/12/2022	Forum Virium Helsinki	Finland	AI4Cities brings together the leading European cities in the intersection of smart cities and GHG emissions reduction, in order to speed up and steer the creation of new breakthrough solutions in how AI will support cities' climate action commitments.
O		iProcureNet	Innovation by developing a European Procurer Networking for security research services	security services	PP	https://www.iprocurenet.eu/	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/832875	H2020-EU.3.7 - Secure societies	01/05/2019	30/04/2024	MINISTERE DE L'INTERIEUR	France	aims to create an ecosystem of procurers, prescribers, legal advisors and other key stakeholders of security procurement, to share procurement trends and needs.
	Y	EAFIP	The European Assistance for Innovation Procurement		PPI	https://eafip.eu/					Convers	Netherlands	The aim of the EAFIP-initiative is to promote good practices and reinforce the evidence base on completed innovation procurements across Europe. To encourage other public procurers to start new PCP and PPI procurements and to boost the digital-green economy recovery through Innovation Procurement (PCP & PPI).
		HAePPI										Europe/ EU	erasmus+ project to develop a training program on public procurement of innovation (PPI) in habitat and e-health sectors
O	Y	PRECIUS	Procurement Educational Consortium for Innovation-sourcing Using Sustainability	Innovation	pp	https://www.utwente.nl/en/ims/etm/precious/	n.a.	KA2 - Cooperation for innovation and the exchange of good practices KA203 - Strategic Partnerships	31/05/2022	30/05/2025	UTwente	Netherlands	With the help of the EXPERTISE project, silver workers are enabled to be upgraded in terms of digital skills so that they can work together inclusively with digital natives in the field of PSM (Purchasing and Supply Management) and develop solutions for current problems.

Protected Data (for GDPR, include data with contacts that gave consent or are publically shared)				Project's assets		
e-mail	other contacts (tel)	First name	Last Name	Interesting Assets (reports, guidelines, tools, events, etc.) to be exploited	description and links to assets	Collaboration history (please use this cell to keep track of contacts/interest)

Figure 5. Projects sheet, all data categories

4. Results

The mapping & scouting activity registered a total number of 371 stakeholders. Below it is represented the percentage for each category:

Category	Percentage
Innovation Demand	15%
Innovation Supply	42.5%
Multipliers	18%
Projects	24.5%

Table 4. Results of mapping & scouting activity

All details can be found in Annex I : Sample extracts from the stakeholders mapping and scouting database

5. Next steps

The compilation of pertinent stakeholders serves as an initial undertaking to advance Task 3.3 and the subsequent activities in Work Package 4 (WP4). More specifically, the acquired stakeholder contacts will be utilized to establish communication and evaluate their level of interest, dedication, and readiness to collaborate in more involved procedures, such as in-depth interviews, feedback provision, or active participation in the development and implementation of project activities. The extent of their involvement in the project's initiatives will also be contingent upon the specific type of support requested. The database will remain open to collect new stakeholders' contact that might be useful for the task's purposes. Different types of engagement methods will be used for training and capacity-building activities in WP4. The engagement strategy will take into consideration also the Value Proposition which was developed in D3.1. In this activity, both innovation procurers and providers shared their tasks, pains and gains. It resulted in a summary of tailored messages for each category that will be used in the following months of the BUILD projects, as shown in the Gantt chart below (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Engagement Gantt chart from D3.1 Value proposition and engagement strategy

Annex I: Sample extracts from the stakeholders mapping and scouting database

1. Innovation Demand

No	Innovation Demand stakeholder type*	Level of activity*	NUTS 2021 classification	Estimated yearly budget for procurement of innovation (if available)	Short description* (to help better define the collaboration strategy in BUILD)
1	Central Purchasing body	National			The office is an independent central body of the state administration, headed by the chairman of the office. In the field of public procurement, it represents the Slovak Republic externally, works in expert working committees of the European Union and actively cooperates with foreign partner institutions. The office ensures the application of public procurement policy in the Slovak Republic.
2	Other	National	NUTS 1: major socio-economic regions	No budget allocated	Government Office's mission is to support the Government of the Republic and the Prime Minister in policy drafting and implementation.
3	Individual Public buyer	City level	NUTS 3: small regions for specific diagnoses	Small (up to 10% of the annual budget)	The University of Tartu is biggest organisation in Tartu City and one of the biggest procurer
4	Other	National	NUTS 1: major socio-economic regions	No budget allocated	Supporting companies
5	Other	National	NUTS 1: major socio-economic regions	No budget allocated	The Estonian Chamber of Commerce and Industry (ECCI) is the oldest and largest Estonian representative organization of entrepreneurs
6	Central Purchasing body	National	NUTS 1: major socio-economic regions	No budget allocated	A non-profit limited company, and act as a central purchasing body for central and local governments in Finland.
7	Regional Purchasing body	Regional	NUTS 1: major socio-economic regions	No budget allocated	A municipality in Southwest Finland region. Turku is doing procurement co-operation with regional municipalities.
8	Regional Purchasing body	Regional	NUTS 1: major socio-economic regions	No budget allocated	A municipality in Southwest Finland region. Turku is doing procurement co-operation with regional municipalities.
9	Regional Purchasing body	Regional	NUTS 1: major socio-economic regions	No budget allocated	A municipality in Southwest Finland region. Turku is doing procurement co-operation with regional municipalities.
10	Regional Purchasing body	Regional	NUTS 1: major socio-economic regions	No budget allocated	A municipality in Southwest Finland region. Turku is doing procurement co-operation with regional municipalities.
11	Regional Purchasing body	Regional	NUTS 1: major socio-economic regions	No budget allocated	A municipality in Southwest Finland region. Turku is doing procurement co-operation with regional municipalities.
12	Regional Purchasing body	Regional	NUTS 1: major socio-economic regions	No budget allocated	A municipality in Southwest Finland region. Turku is doing procurement co-operation with regional municipalities.
13	Regional Purchasing body	Regional	NUTS 1: major socio-economic regions	No budget allocated	A municipality in Southwest Finland region. Turku is doing procurement co-operation with regional municipalities.
14	Regional Purchasing body	Regional	NUTS 1: major socio-economic regions	No budget allocated	A municipality in Southwest Finland region. Turku is doing procurement co-operation with regional municipalities.
15	Regional Purchasing body	Regional	NUTS 1: major socio-economic regions	No budget allocated	A municipality in Southwest Finland region. Turku is doing procurement co-operation with regional municipalities.

2. Innovation Supply

No	Application field of their innovation relevant for BUILD*	Short description of the innovation proposed* (to help better define the collaboration strategy in BUILD)
1	Green mobility	develops, manufactures and sells heating systems for vehicles and other applications. The increasing pressure for more efficient and greener heating systems encouraged Kabola to develop Kabola Blue Ecoline (KB Eco) series.
3	Bioeconomy	FINISHING LEATHER WITH BIOPOLYMERS ADDED WITH NANOCOMPONENTS
4	Circular economy	Recycling shredded used tyres and rubber waste into personalized recovered Carbon Black to limit use of fossil fuels and carbon dioxide emission
5	Circular economy	FINISHING LEATHER WITH BIOPOLYMERS ADDED WITH NANOCOMPONENTS
6	Company training	Innovative model of a simultaneous translation service
7	Circular economy	Whey2Value: Valorising waste whey into high-value products
8	Bioeconomy	Innovative Biodegradable PLA Plastic for an Increased Range of Packaging Applications
9	Bioeconomy	Commercialisation of expanded bed biofilm reactor technology for the treatment of waste-
10	Bioeconomy	INNOVATIVE FUNCTIONAL PAINT FOR AIR PURIFICATION
11	Circular economy	Arena-Master Mobile Solution for Complete Synthetic Turf Recycling On-site
26	Circular economy	Mushroom and biogas production in a circular economy
14	Circular economy	Application of Microbial Fuel Cells for waste water treatment
15	Circular economy	GRen Desalination: A closed-loop technology for full recovery of water and raw materials from the wastewater effluent
16	Circular economy	Sustainable thermal packaging from waste feathers
17	Bioeconomy	Innovative biopesticides production: valorisation of endemic plants and green industrial residues
18	Bioeconomy	Development of eco-friendly architectural coil coatings for clean buildings and pollution-free air
19	Circular economy	INTERnational COMmercialization of innovative products based on MicroalgaE
20	Circular economy	Farming high value algae with industrial gas emissions
21	Circular economy	Efficient Aluminium Salt cake Recycling Technology

3. Multipliers

ID	Multiplier stakeholder type*	Level of activity*	Short description of their activity*	Why relevant for BUILD* (to help better define the collaboration strategy in BUILD)
1	Advisors/consultancy/legal	National	Procurio provides public procurement services for both the public and private sectors. It specializes in electronic public procurement, the electronicization of public procurement processes as well as the optimization of public procurement management in the organization.	
2	Intermediary (e.g. chambers of commerce, development agencies)	International	VTT is one of Europe's leading research institutions. We are owned by the Finnish state. We advance the utilisation and commercialisation of research and technology in commerce and society. Through scientific and technological means, we turn large global challenges into sustainable growth for businesses and society.	Research and expertise on innovation procurement. Wide network.
3	National center for Public Administration training	National	Motiva provides the public sector, businesses, municipalities and consumers with information, solutions and services that allow them to make resource-efficient, effective and sustainable choices	National networks, training and tools related to sustainable procurement.
4	Other	National	Government organisation for innovation funding and trade, travel and investment promotion.	Funding for innovation procurement, related clusters and networks.
5	National center for Public Administration training	National	KEINO is a network-based Competence center for Sustainable and Innovative public procurement in Finland	Excellence network, events and tools for public procurers
6	Policy Maker	National	An advocate for all Finnish municipalities, promotes local self-government and the modernisation of municipal services.	Network and excellence (procurement, legal) related to municipalities
7	Other	National	The Finnish Environment Institute (Syke) offers expertise and independent information on global phenomena such as climate change, biodiversity loss, overconsumption, pollution and eutrophication.	Research on sustainable procurement
8	Other	EU	A higher education institution of 12,000 experts, researchers, students, faculty members and teaching professionals. Creates solutions locally and globally. As a significant regional actor, we harbour close ties to businesses and municipalities in Southwest Finland. Turku UAS is the fourth largest technical university in Finland.	Research on procurement. Local networks and case studies. Business and innovation development.
10	Intermediary (e.g. chambers of commerce, development agencies)	Regional	Turku Science Park Ltd. is a non-profit development company for the entire Turku subregion that works in close cooperation with local, national and international actors in the fields of business and economic development.	Local business networks and innovation development excellence.
9	National center for Public Administration training	National	The main objective of the Entrepriise Estonia is to support entrepreneurship and the improvement of living conditions in Estonia, increase our international competitiveness, visibility and attractiveness as a place for business, living and studies.	Excellence center for Estonia
10	Policy Maker	National	The Ministry of Finance is the responsible institution for public procurement policy, drafting the law, providing supervision and consulting.	Policy maker
11	National center for Public Administration training	National	A Competence center for Sustainable public procurement in Finland	Excellence network, events and tools for public procurers
12	Intermediary (e.g. chambers of commerce, development agencies)	National	The innovative cities and communities consist of 16 Finnish urban regions that are aiming to be international pioneers in sustainable urban development and evolving business.	InnoCities use cooperation to create innovation and innovation to create sustainability.
13	Other	National	Ministry of finance and an advocate for all Finnish municipalities forms a programme that advances effectiveness of Finland's public procurement.	The programme includes themed networks and one of the networks concentrates on innovative procurement. Network includes municipalities, public organizations, private consultation organizations and businesses.
14	Intermediary (e.g. chambers of commerce, development agencies)	National	Boost is a Turku-based entrepreneurship society that inspires and helps young students become startup entrepreneurs.	Boost has a network of innovative startups
15	Intermediary (e.g. chambers of commerce, development agencies)	National	Suomen Yrittäjät is an interest and service organization for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) from all fields around entire Finland and their owners.	Suomen yrittäjät has a large network of SMEs
16	Intermediary (e.g. chambers of commerce, development agencies)	Regional	Varsinais-Suomen Yrittäjät is an interest and service organization for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) from all fields around Turku region.	Varsinais-Suomen yrittäjät has a large network of SMEs
17	Intermediary (e.g. chambers of commerce, development agencies)	National	Forum for Sustainable Procurement was set up by the Minister for the Environment in May 2011 to promote environmentally conscious and responsible procurement of goods and services among professional buyers - both in public and private companies.	
18	Intermediary (e.g. chambers of commerce, development agencies)	International	The Global SCP Clearinghouse is targeted at governments, the business sector, researchers, civil society, mass media, among other actors. It covers all themes and sectors relevant to SCP as well as all regions. The Global SCP Clearinghouse builds on and links to many existing websites and portals, providing new and interactive functions to strengthen cooperation and inspire more action for SCP.	
19	European Institution	EU	The Lead Market Initiative is the European policy for 6 important sectors that are supported by actions to lower barriers to bring new products or services onto the market.	
20	European Institution	EU	The Eco-Innovation Observatory functions as a platform for the structured collection and analysis of an extensive range of eco-innovation information, gathered from across the European Union. It is a 3-year initiative financed by DG Environment under the CIP programme.	
21	Other	EU	Clean Vehicles Portal	

4. Projects

	Ongoing/C oncluded O/C	Relevant for collaboration Y/N/M (Maybe)	Project Acronym	Full name	Area	Domain
1	O	Y	BUILD	Building Capacities in Innovation Procurement for Cities	innovation procurement	PPI
2	O	Y	InnoFacilitator	Health InnoFacilitator the European Facilitator Community Promoting Public Procurement of Innovation in Healthcare	Health	IP
3	O	Y	PROTECT	Preparing a Pre-Commercial Procurement for end-user services based on environmental observation in the area of climate change adaptation and mitigation	climate change, earth observation	IP
4	O	M	CircularPSP	Public Service Platforms for Circular, Innovative and Resilient Municipalities through PCP	circular economy	PCP
5	O	Y	InnoBuyer	Fast track to innovation procurement		PPI
6	O	Y	CITIES 4.0	Climate Innovation Through Interactive Ecosystem Summits		PPI
7	C	Y	Procure2Innovate	European network of competence centres for innovation procurement	competence centers	
8	C	M	AI4Cities	AI accelerating Cities transition to carbon neutrality	artificial intelligence, carbon neutrality of cities	PCP
9	O		iProcureNet	Innovation by developing a European Procurer Networking for security research services	security services	PP
10		Y	EAFIP	The European Assistance for Innovation Procurement		PPI
11			HAePPI			
12	O	Y	PRECIUS	Procurement Educational Consortium for Innovation-sourcing Using Sustainability	Innovation	PP
13	C	N	E+ PERSIST			
14	O	M	EXPERTISE	Experienced Purchasers Education Research Transfer for Industry 4.0 Skills Expertise	Private purchasing and supply management / procurement skills in the digital age (private sector)	Industry 4.0